

POLITICAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF CIVIL SOCIETY DEVELOPMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20621050>

Annotation. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the political and legal foundations of the development of civil society institutions within the framework of the modern Development Strategy of Uzbekistan. The implementation of international standards for the protection of human rights into national legislation, the strict definition of the legal status of the mahalla (self-governing bodies of citizens) in the updated Constitution are socio-politically justified.

Keywords: Development strategy, civil society, rule of law, human rights, Constitution, mahalla assembly, non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs), public associations, Ombudsman, sense of involvement.

The level of democratic development of any state and its influence in the international community are determined by the degree to which the institutions of a free civil society are formed in it and the rule of law is ensured. At a new stage of Uzbekistan's independent development, a fundamental reform of the socio-political and legal system, the establishment of a constructive dialogue between the state and society have been identified as a strategic task. The Development Strategy, which is currently being studied by the general public and international experts, opens up new horizons for the modernization of our country. In this process, the role of the state as a subject of political governance, the integration of international human rights standards into the national legal space, and the strengthening of the foundations of a strong civil society serve as objects of topical scientific and practical research.

The current state of development of Uzbekistan proves that democratic reforms are being carried out in the country with great speed, the formation of civil society and the establishment of a legal state. Today, the development strategy, which is widely interpreted and studied by domestic and foreign experts and scientists, and is given a unique assessment, and the further prospects for the socio-political and economic development of the country in all its directions are separately defined.

Every state strives to ensure a stable political environment, create conditions conducive to the development of all spheres of society, and for this, it is natural that "the state, as a subject of political governance, as well as the main political institution that has accumulated maximum power" [1], develops a political and legal mechanism and uses existing resources.

The independent state of Uzbekistan is implementing its policy - the development of a new system of governance in the country and the transition to market relations, in accordance with the specific features of the transition to market relations, paying special attention to the groups and strata that form the basis of its social relations, taking into account their goals, interests and problems.

As is known, every nation has the right to a free and prosperous life and considers it precious. In particular, every person has such a right. About 70 international conventions,

declarations, and pacts on human rights have been adopted by the UN, more than 160 by the General Assembly of the Council of Europe, more than 70 by UNESCO, and more than 30 by the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe. Currently, there are about 400 international documents on human rights [2].

During the years of independence, a legal space has been created in Uzbekistan, based on new internationally accepted legal principles and requirements, stemming from the primacy of human rights and freedoms. A sharp turn has been made from the oppression and violence of the authoritarian regime to legal norms that meet world standards. An effective mechanism has been created to harmonize the laws of our country with universal human norms and standards in the field of human rights, develop a national action program in this area, establish an integrated system of institutions protecting human rights, continue to accede to international treaties and documents on human rights, and fulfill obligations under them.

Civil society is a society of people with high qualities. Civil society is a social system in which the rule of law is ensured, human rights and freedoms are established, political parties and institutions, the diversity of ideologies and opinions is ensured, a person is guaranteed the free choice of forms of his economic, political and cultural life, and the status of citizens' self-government bodies is high.

Political foundations. The need for strong political foundations for building a new society is a fact that has been proven many times in the process of historical development. Today, Uzbekistan, which has become an equal member of the world community, has created a political system and structures of new content and form. An electoral system that meets international standards has been formed, the foundations of a democratic state and a free civil society with the rule of law have been strengthened, and the system for ensuring human rights and freedoms has been further improved. In every society and country, unless the social consciousness of different layers of the people, parties, and national-ethnic units changes, it is difficult for the people and nation living there to realize their ultimate goals. Harmonious resolution of these issues from the first years of independence will help form the socio-political foundations that will allow for the implementation of priority tasks in this regard.

Legal basis. It is appropriate to first mention the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan as the core of the legal basis for the establishment and functioning of civil society institutions. In the words of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, "The consolidation of the basic principles of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations in our Constitution in the early years of our independence created favorable conditions for the development of a wide network of such organizations that reflect the interests of all segments of the population" [3].

The status of citizens' self-government bodies is defined as a legal norm in Article 127 of the updated Constitution as follows:

"In towns, villages and villages, as well as in neighborhoods in cities, towns, villages and villages, citizens' assemblies are self-government bodies, which elect a chairman.

Citizens' self-government bodies are not part of the system of state authorities and have the right to independently resolve issues of local importance in accordance with the law, proceeding from the interests of citizens, historical specifics of development, as well as national values, local customs and traditions.

The state creates the necessary conditions for the implementation of the activities of citizens' self-government bodies, assists them in the exercise of their powers established by law.

The procedure for the election of citizens' self-government bodies, the organization of their activities and powers are determined by law" [4].

The Law "On Citizens' Self-Government Bodies", adopted on September 2, 1993 at the third session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the twelfth convocation, determined the legal status of citizens' self-government bodies established in villages, towns and villages, as well as in the neighborhoods within them.

Among the laws that serve to build civil society in our country, we can mention the following: the Law "On Public Associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Law "On Trade Unions, Their Rights and Guarantees of Their Activities", the Law "On Non-Governmental and Non-Profit Organizations", the Law "On Political Parties", the Law "On Financing of Political Parties", the Law "On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations", the Law "On Mass Media", etc. The creation of these legal frameworks not only led to the emergence of an independent sphere of legal regulation of social relations related to the activities of public organizations in the national legislative system of our country, but also gave it a sense of systematization. Along with the above, issues related to the protection of the rights of public organizations have created an opportunity to form a whole legislative system, encompassing constitutional, civil, administrative, and criminal law.

Issues affecting the interests of public organizations are resolved by state authorities and local self-government bodies with the participation and agreement of relevant public organizations. At the same time, it was determined that the state must ensure compliance with the legitimate interests and rights of public organizations, provide comprehensive assistance to their activities, in particular, provide benefits in tax and other matters.

In recent years, the Law "On Public Funds" and the Law "On Patronage", the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Promote the Development of Civil Society Institutions in Uzbekistan" and other relevant documents have been adopted. These are playing an important role in strengthening the social activity of civil society institutions.

Reforms in the process of forming and developing civil society institutions, which are the basis of civil society, are increasingly deepening in the country. Currently, more than 9 thousand non-governmental and non-profit organizations of republican significance, as well as state-registered ones, operate in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent and the regions.

In our country, the Human Rights Ombudsman of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Ombudsman), the National Center for Human Rights, the Institute for Monitoring Current Legislation, as well as the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Prosecutor General's Office, and the Ministry of Internal Affairs have been created and are actively working.

The fact that centuries-old and historically significant changes have been implemented in our country during the years of independence is reflected in the socio-political, economic, cultural and educational spheres of life. Each historical period acquires its own unique characteristics and requires the development of new tasks and mechanisms for their implementation.

In this sense, the historical path taken by our people during the years of independence, the great achievements and milestones achieved in all areas, and the importance of our country's Development Strategy have become the main direction of our spiritual and educational work today. This places a huge responsibility on all of us to create a sense of belonging to the reforms being implemented in society, to live with the results achieved during independent development in the minds of various segments of the population, especially the younger generation.

Thus, the report of the head of our state, based on historical evidence and figures, profound scientific ideas and conclusions, undoubtedly serves as a solid theoretical basis for a deep study of the history of our Motherland's independence, the stages of development of our society, the essence and content of today's priority areas and tasks, and a clearer understanding of its specific features and modern opportunities in the present days, when the process of applying this national experience in other countries has begun.

In conclusion, the reforms being rapidly carried out within the framework of Uzbekistan's modern Development Strategy have created a political and legal mechanism for transforming civil society from a mere declarative concept into a real social force. The coordinating role of the state as a subject of political governance and the integral incorporation of the requirements of more than 400 international instruments on the protection of human rights into national legislation indicate the formation of a solid legal space in our country.

The strengthening of the mahalla as a self-governing institution, independent of the state power system, at the constitutional level has formed a unique model of civil society based on Uzbek, national values and traditions. The fact that more than 9 thousand NGOs operate in the republic and an integrated system of institutions such as the Ombudsman and the National Center for Human Rights has been established indicates that public control and pluralism are working in practice.

The main strategic task today is to systematically instill the essence of these historical achievements and political and legal reforms in the minds of every citizen, especially the younger generation. Raising the sense of involvement of members of society as "active participants" in reforms, rather than "observers", serves as an absolute guarantee of the stability of the legal state and a prosperous civil society being built.

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